

Soap Film based Artificial Photosynthesis

D2.1

Database of transport coefficients in Matlab environment

Report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

We provide here the deliverable **D2.1: Database of transport coefficient in Matlab environment** as a part of the work-package WP2 - R&D Platforms and Soap Film Model of the H2020 FET-Open project SoFiA (GA 828838). The main objective of the present work is to collect literature data of diffusion coefficients and equilibrium adsorption data (i.e. Henry's law constants) for gas species involved in the targeted photosynthesis process. In particular, details are given on the sources of these data and how they enter the models to be developed that will be used to describe the transport phenomena of gaseous species. Finally, this document is complemented with the hereby attached database in Matlab format.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The study of the diffusion mechanisms taking place at the gas-liquid interface and across soap films are expected to significantly affect the photosynthesis process envisioned in the SoFiA project.

More specifically, the diffusion coefficients will be crucial in the description of diffusion processes in diluted species and in gas mixtures, with Fick's law being applied in the first case, whereas Stefan-Maxwell equations being necessary to represent the mutual interactions between gases. Furthermore, the Henry's law, relating the equilibrium concentration of gases in the liquid film and their molar fraction in the gaseous phase above, will be also important as it governs the absorption phenomena at the gas-liquid interface.

In order to start building a Multiphysics model of the envisioned soap-film based membranes, we have summarized in this document the diffusion coefficients and the Henry's law constants of the different gases and their dependence on the temperature at ambient pressure.

2. DATABASE STRUCTURE

We have collected diffusion coefficient in an Excel file entitled "Database_D.xlsx", whereas a Matlab function, "Henry_Const.m", has been created in order to calculate the Henry's law constants. The two files are called by a main Matlab file, "main_D_H.m", which imports the Excel database and gives some examples of how the Henry's law constants function works.

2.1 Diffusion coefficients: The Excel database summarizes the diffusion coefficients in $[m^2/s]$ and it is composed by three tables organized in three different sheets: one with the gas diffusion coefficients in water, "D_water", one with the self-diffusion coefficients, "D_self", and a third one with the mutual gas diffusion coefficients, "D_mutual".

2.2 Henry's law constants: The Henry's law constant calculation has been implemented in a Matlab function. Receiving as an input a string with the name of the gas and a number corresponding to the temperature in Kelvin, it calculates the Henry's law constant, H , $[mol/(m^3 Pa)]$ for the given gas in water:

```
function [H] = Henry_Const (gas, T)
```

3. DIFFUSION COEFFICIENTS

3.1 Diffusion of dilute species: In the transport of gaseous species in dilute solutions, the diffusion flux depends on the concentration gradient following Fick's first law:

$$N_i = -D_i \nabla c_i \quad (1)$$

where N_i is the molar flux, c_i is the concentration and D_i is the diffusion coefficient of the i -gas. In case of a transient process, considering the continuity equation for the mass, we can write:

$$\frac{\partial c_i}{\partial t} = D_i \nabla^2 c_i \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) assumes a constant D , which is valid only when the solute molecules are order of magnitudes lower than the solvent ones. Such an assumption is accurate in the case of gas diffusion in liquids.

Table 1 summarizes the experimental values found in literature of the diffusion coefficient of the five main species involved in the photosynthesis process studied in SoFiA project (i.e. CO, CO₂, O₂, H₂ and H⁺), all of them are in the order of $10^{-9} m^2/s$. Notice that multiple values for the same gas found from disparate literature sources were reported separately in Table 1.

Table 1: Gas diffusion coefficients in water

Substance	D_{1w}	T	Reference
	[m ² /s]	[K]	
H+	9.31E-09	298.15	(1)
CO ₂	1.26E-09	283.15	(1)
CO ₂	1.45E-09	288.15	(1)
CO ₂	1.67E-09	293.15	(1)
CO ₂	1.91E-09	298.15	(1)
CO ₂	2.17E-09	303.15	(1)
CO ₂	2.47E-09	308.15	(1)
CO ₂	1.96E-09	298.15	(2)
H ₂	1.92E-09	298.15	(3)
H ₂	3.62E-09	283.15	(1)
H ₂	4.08E-09	288.15	(1)
H ₂	4.58E-09	293.15	(1)
H ₂	5.11E-09	298.15	(1)
H ₂	5.69E-09	303.15	(1)
H ₂	6.31E-09	308.15	(1)
H ₂	3.19E-09	283.15	(4)
H ₂	4.50E-09	298.15	(4)
H ₂	5.91E-09	313.15	(4)
H ₂	5.85E-09	298.15	(2)
H ₂	4.50E-09	298.15	(3)
CO	1.07E-09	283.15	(5)
CO	2.03E-09	293.15	(5)
CO	2.43E-09	303.15	(5)
CO	3.62E-09	313.15	(5)
O ₂	2.50E-09	298.15	(2)
O ₂	1.67E-09	288.15	(1)
O ₂	2.01E-09	293.15	(1)
O ₂	2.42E-09	298.15	(1)

From the gathered data, we briefly report below a few examples on the adopted diffusion coefficients measurements.

Proton diffusivity in water has been calculated at 25°C by using the following relation (1):

$$D = \left(\frac{RT}{F^2} \right) \left(\frac{\lambda}{|z|} \right) \quad (3)$$

where λ is the molar equivalent conductivity measured by Macinnes et al. (6), R is the molar gas constant, T the temperature, F the Faraday constant, and z the charge on the ion.

CO₂ and H₂ diffusion in distilled water for a temperature range of 5 - 35 °C has been studied in (7). Here, the experimental apparatus consisted in two chambers with initial different concentration, separated by a water

diaphragm made by a packing of glass spheres with 125 μm diameter held together with two nets of stainless steel. The whole apparatus was immersed in a constant temperature water bath. Under those conditions, Authors have obtained the following equation describing concentration variation over time:

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = m \left\{ (t - T_l) + \frac{12}{\pi^2} T_l \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\left(\frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n^2} \right) \exp \left(\frac{n^2 \pi^2 t}{6 T_l} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

The diffusion coefficient, D , is calculated from T_l and m which are measured experimentally and are the time lag necessary to the gas to cross the diaphragm and a parameter directly linked to the diffusion coefficient through the following formulas, respectively:

$$T_l = \frac{d^2}{6D} \text{ and } m = \frac{\alpha D}{d h_{eff}}, \quad (5) (6)$$

being d the diaphragm thickness, h_{eff} the ratio between the gas chamber volume and the diaphragm surface and α the dimensionless solubility (Ostwald coefficient) of the gas in water. In **equation (4)** the exponential function considers the nonlinear behavior during the first phase of the measurements for $t < 4 T_l$. On the other hand, the $\frac{c}{c_0} = m (t - T_l)$ term represents the linear dependence between concentration and time.

In the work of Ferrel *et al.* (4), authors have used an experimental apparatus which measured the gas diffusion between two carboys, one filled by degassed water and the other with water rich in hydrogen. The hydrogen diffused through a long and thin stainless-steel tube (length $L = 600 \text{ cm}$, radius $R = 0.202 \text{ cm}$) and its concentration variation was detected by using a mass spectrometer. An isothermal laminar flow in a cylindrical duct ruled by the diffusion was assumed and the bulk average concentration change as function of time is derived by the following properly simplified equation:

$$C = \frac{C_0}{2} \operatorname{erfc} \left[\frac{L - u_{0.5} t}{(4 k_{0.5} t)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right] \quad (7)$$

where C_0 is concentration of solute gas at the input and $u_{0.5} = \frac{L}{t_{0.5}}$, being $t_{0.5}$ the time at which the experimental bulk average concentration reaches $C_0/2$. The diffusion coefficient is contained in $k_{0.5} = \frac{R^2 u_{0.5}^2}{48 D}$.

The technique employed by Wise *et al.* (5) (8) for measuring CO and other gas diffusion coefficients involved a transparent horizontal cell full of deionized water with a dissolving bubble injected inside with a hypodermic syringe. The diffusion coefficient, D_L , was obtained by the shrinkage rate of the bubble in the following way:

$$D_L = \frac{3m}{\alpha} \left(\frac{273}{T} \right) \left(\frac{P}{P - p} \right) \times 10^{-5} \left[\frac{\text{cm}^2}{\text{sec}} \right], \quad (8)$$

being α the Bunsen solubility coefficient that for an ideal gas is strictly related to the Henry's law constant by $H = \frac{\alpha}{R T^{STP}}$ with $T^{STP} = 273.15 \text{ [K]}$ (9), p the water vapor pressure and P the total barometric pressure. Finally, m is a fitting parameter defined as $D^2 = D_0^2 - mt$, where D and D_0 are the bubble diameters measured by a microscope at time t and 0 [s] , respectively.

3.2 Diffusion of concentrated species: In case of gas mixtures, inter-molecular dependencies of the various gas species are considered by applying the Maxwell-Stefan model. In that description, the diffusion coefficient of the Fick's relation, **equation (1)**, is more accurately substituted by a tensor that contains the self and mutual diffusion coefficients, while the diffusive mass fluxes of the various species are now taken into account.

We have summarized the experimental values of the self-diffusion coefficients of $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$, H_2 , O_2 , CO and CO_2 in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Self-diffusion coefficients for $H_2O_{(g)}$, H_2 , O_2 , CO and CO_2

Gas	D_{11}	T	Reference
	[m ² /s]	[K]	
$H_2O_{(g)}$	2.76E-05	273.15	(3)
H_2	1.60E-04	273.15	(3)
H_2	1.24E-04	300.15	(10)
O_2	1.92E-05	273.15	(3)
O_2	1.85E-05	273.15	(11)
O_2	2.09E-05	293.15	(11)
O_2	2.35E-05	313.15	(11)
CO_2	1.06E-05	273.15	(3)
CO_2	9.74E-06	273.15	(12)
CO_2	1.13E-05	298.15	(12)
CO_2	9.70E-06	273.15	(13)
CO_2	1.25E-05	313.15	(13)
CO	1.90E-05	273.15	(14)
CO	2.47E-05	319.75	(14)

As for the previous paragraph, we provide here below a short review of some experimental methods employed to measure data reported in **Table 2**.

Winn (12) estimated the self-diffusion coefficient of carbon dioxide and other gases adopting two cylindrical brass bulbs of 357 cm² connected through a brass tube, one filled by a gas and the other filled with the same gas enriched by an isotope. The mixture composition of one chamber was monitored continuously by a mass spectrometer. Hence, the diffusion of the tracer isotope into normal isotope, D_{12} , was obtained. Finally, the self-diffusion coefficient, D_{11} , was calculated with the **equation (9)** proposed by (15):

$$D_{11} = D_{12} \left[2 \frac{M_2}{M_1 + M_2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (9)$$

where M_1 and M_2 are the masses of the two isotopes.

Amdur *et al.* (13) (14) have investigated the self-diffusion coefficients of CO_2 and CO by using a long horizontal tube divided by a central slide in two chambers, one filled by the gas with radioactive tracers and in the other by same pure gas, provided with an electrode each. The two electrodes ionized the gas generating a current that was measured. When, the separating slide was opened, the rate of diffusion was followed by evaluating the decrease in the ionization current as a function of time from:

$$\frac{i(t)}{i(0)} = \eta + \theta \exp(-k^2 D t) \quad (10)$$

where $i(t)$ and $i(0)$ are the ionization currents at $t=0$ and $t=t$, η and θ are parameters determined by experimental measurements, k is a constant depending on the given apparatus and the initial conditions and D is the diffusion coefficient.

Table 3 shows the mutual diffusion coefficients for $H_2O_{(g)}$, H_2 , O_2 , CO and CO_2 .

Table 3: Mutual diffusion coefficients for $H_2O_{(g)}$, H_2 , O_2 , CO and CO_2

Gas1	Gas2	D_{12}	T	Reference
		[m ² /s]	[K]	

CO	CO ₂	1.37E-05	273.15	(2)
CO	CO ₂	1.62E-05	293.15	(1)
CO	CO ₂	2.50E-05	373.15	(1)
CO ₂	H ₂ O _(g)	1.38E-05	273.15	(2)
CO ₂	H ₂ O _(g)	1.62E-05	293.15	(1)
CO ₂	H ₂ O _(g)	2.02E-05	307.45	(16)
CO	H ₂ O _(g)	2.51E-05 ¹	293.15	(17)
CO	O ₂	1.85E-05	273.15	(2)
CO	O ₂	2.02E-05	293.15	(1)
CO	O ₂	3.07E-05	373.15	(1)
CO ₂	O ₂	1.39E-05	273.15	(2)
CO ₂	O ₂	1.59E-05	293.15	(1)
CO ₂	O ₂	2.48E-05	373.15	(1)
H ₂ O _(g)	O ₂	2.44E-05	293.15	(1)
H ₂ O _(g)	O ₂	4.03E-05	373.15	(1)
H ₂ O _(g)	O ₂	2.82E-05	308.05	(16)
H ₂	CO	6.51E-05	273.15	(2)
H ₂	CO	6.86E-05	273.15	(1)
H ₂	CO	7.72E-05	293.15	(1)
H ₂	CO ₂	5.50E-05	273.15	(2)
H ₂	CO ₂	6.46E-05	298.15	(2)
H ₂	CO ₂	5.52E-05	273.15	(1)
H ₂	CO ₂	4.12E-05	293.15	(1)
H ₂	O ₂	6.97E-05	273.15	(2)
H ₂	O ₂	6.92E-05	273.15	(1)
H ₂	O ₂	7.56E-05	293.15	(1)
H ₂	H ₂ O _(g)	7.50E-05	273.15	(2)

Lide *et al.* (1) presented a relevant amount of data based on the work by Marrero *et al.* (18). In (18), an extensive literature review on the gaseous diffusion coefficients of binary mixtures and detailed analysis of experimental methods had been performed.

Finally, the CO-H₂O_(g) diffusion coefficient was estimated by using the empirical correlation proposed by Fuller *et al.* (17) which is valid also for polar molecules (unlike the Chapman-Enskog kinetic theory (19)). They estimated the mutual diffusion coefficient, D_{12} , of a gas mixture from the temperature T , the pressure p , the molecular weight of the gases, M_1 and M_2 , and the special atomic diffusion volumes, $\Sigma_1 v_i$ and $\Sigma_2 v_i$ using the following relation:

$$D_{12} = \frac{10^{-3} T^{1.75} \left(\frac{1}{M_1} + \frac{1}{M_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{p \left[(\Sigma_1 v_i)^{\frac{1}{3}} + (\Sigma_2 v_i)^{\frac{1}{3}} \right]^2} \quad (11)$$

$\Sigma_1 v_i$ and $\Sigma_2 v_i$ have the dimensions of atomic volumes and are parameters that depend on the gas type, their numerical values of $\Sigma_1 v_i$ and $\Sigma_2 v_i$ are reported in **Table 4**.

¹ Value obtained by theoretical calculations

Table 4 Special atomic diffusion volumes of $H_2O_{(g)}$, H_2 , O_2 , CO and CO_2

Gas	M	Diffusion volumes
	[g/mol]	
O_2	31.999	16.6
CO_2	44.01	26.9
CO	28.01	18.9
$H_2O_{(g)}$	18.016	12.7
H_2	2.016	7.07

Table 5 shows the mutual gas diffusion coefficients estimated both with the Chapman-Enskog kinetic theory (data from (19)) and with **equation (11)** at $T=293$ K and $p=1$ atm. We can see that the latter gives a better estimation.

Table 5 Comparison between experimental data, theoretical models and empirical correlations

Gas pair	Experimental data from	Chapman-Enskog (19)		Fuller <i>et al.</i> (17)	
	D_{12}	D_{12}	Relative Error	D_{12}	Relative error
	[m ² /s]	[m ² /s]	[%]	[m ² /s]	[%]
O_2 - CO_2	1.59E-05	1.46E-05	8.19%	1.57E-05	1.38%
O_2 - CO	2.02E-05	1.98E-05	1.80%	1.98E-05	2.17%
O_2 - H_2O	2.44E-05	2.03E-05	16.62%	2.56E-05	5.10%
CO_2 - CO	1.62E-05	1.46E-05	9.71%	1.57E-05	3.27%
CO_2 - H_2O	1.62E-05	1.42E-05	12.52%	2.05E-05	26.25%
CO - H_2O		2.00E-05		2.51E-05	

4. HENRY'S LAW CONSTANTS

The Henry's law states that at constant temperature, the equilibrium concentration c_a of a gas species in a given volume of liquid depends on the partial pressure p of the gas itself as follows:

$$H = \frac{c_a}{p} \left[\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3 \text{Pa}} \right], \quad (12)$$

being H the popular Henry's law constant.

Although various relations are proposed in literature, we report below an Arrhenius type equation for describing the dependence of the Henry's constant on temperature for CO_2 , CO and O_2 in water (20):

$$H = \frac{1}{101.325} \exp \left(A + \frac{B}{T} + C \log(T) \right) \left[\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3 \text{Pa}} \right] \quad (13)$$

where the constants A , B and C are reported in **Table 6** and T is the temperature in [K].

Table 6: Equation (13) constants for pure water

Gas	A	B	C	Range of validity	
				[K]	[K]
O_2	-161.6	8160	22.39	273	348
CO	-178	8750	24.875	278	323

CO ₂	-145.1	8350	19.96	273	353
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The Henry's law constant for H₂ has been calculated by the following equation, valid from 274 to 339 [K] (9) (21):

$$H = H_0 \exp\left(\frac{d \log(H)}{d\left(\frac{1}{T}\right)}\right) \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{298.15}\right) \left[\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3 \text{Pa}}\right] \quad (14)$$

where $\frac{d \log(H)}{d\left(\frac{1}{T}\right)} = 490 \text{ [K]}$ and $H_0 = 7.7 \cdot 10^{-6} \left[\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3 \text{Pa}}\right]$.

Table 7 shows the Henry's Law Constants at 293.15 K in different unit measures for the studied species. The unit conversion has been performed as follows:

$$H \left[\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3 \text{Pa}}\right] = \frac{H_1}{101.325} \left[\frac{\text{M}}{\text{atm}}\right] = \frac{H_2}{R T} [-] \quad (15)$$

where R is the gas constant in [J/(K mol)] and T is the temperature in [K].

Table 7 Henry's law constants at 293.15 [K] for pure water

Gas	H	H ₁	H ₂
	[mol/(m ³ Pa)]	[M/atm]	[-]
O ₂	1.37E-05	1.40E-03	3.36E-02
CO ₂	3.90E-04	3.96E-02	9.52E-01
CO	1.05E-05	1.07E-03	2.56E-02
H ₂	7.91E-06	8.02E-04	1.93E-02

5. CONCLUSIONS

We carried out a comprehensive literature review to collect the diffusion parameters necessary for modeling the gas transport across the soap film based membranes envisioned in the SoFiA project. Furthermore, we have collected data to calculate the Henry's law constants ruling the equilibrium gas concentration in the envisioned photosynthetic membranes (i.e. liquid phases). Those data can be recalled by two Matlab files that make use of a diffusion coefficient database and the Henry's law constant function. We attach to the present report the following files: 1) "Database_D.xlsx" (Excel file); 2) "main_D_H.m" (Matlab file); 3) "Henry_Const.m" (Matlab file); 4) "readme.txt". Notice that the attached software has been tested under the R2016a Matlab release (64-bit).

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